

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON OFF-AXIS TENSILE INITIAL FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF GLASS PLAIN FABRIC/UNSATURATED POLYMER (UP) COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A number of off-axis tests for glass plain fabric/Unsaturated polymer (UP) composites considering different fiber orientations are carried out and are accompanied with acoustic emission (AE) registration to study the initial fracture behavior of the composites. The AE data revealed that the damage development thresholds are lower for the composites at $\theta = 0, 5, \text{ and } 10^\circ$ indicating an earlier onset of damage. The composites at $\theta = 0, 5, \text{ and } 10^\circ$ exhibited a significantly increased AE activity, both in terms of the number of events and the energy level. There is little variation for initial fracture strain obtained from three methods including knee point method, AE events method and AE energy method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites have been increasingly and extensively employed for various application areas including aeronautical and automotive parts, sporting equipment as well as wind generator blades and other products on the account of their outstanding mechanical properties, superior strength-to-weight ratios and non-corrosiveness in recent decades [1-4]. In order to derive the maximum benefit from such advanced anisotropic woven fabric composites, there is a strong need for more refined analysis taking into account the failure behaviour of composites under multiaxial loadings.

The study of off-axis behaviors of the various composites have been reported by many researchers. In the research of Bergmann et al.[5], the woven fabric composites under quasi-static and high strain-rate $\pm 45^\circ$ off-axis tensile loading was investigated, assessing the nonlinear stress-strain behaviour and weight-specific energy absorption capability under different loading rates. The results showed that strain rate has significant effects on the mechanical properties and energy absorption of the material. Zhou et al. [6] investigated the mechanical properties of unidirectional (UD) and woven fabric glass/epoxy composites under off-axis tensile loading. The experimental results indicated that both off-axis elastic modulus and strength degrade with increasing off-axis angle in all cases, and the woven fabric composites present nonlinear stress-strain behavior under off-axial tension loading. The prediction results demonstrated that the Tsai-Wu criterion can be used successfully to analyze failure properties of the woven fabric composites under multiaxial stress conditions.

Acoustic emission (AE) is defined as the generation of transient elastic waves by the rapid release of energy from localized sources within a material undergoing deformation. To monitor the damage process, acoustic emission (AE) is widely used in evaluating damage characteristics during mechanical properties tests. Xingmin Zhuang and Xiong Yan [7] investigated different fracture behaviors bring about different AE signals responding on amplitude events. In the research, different events occurred inside the materials included fiber-matrix interfacial debonding, matrix plastic deformation and cracking, fiber pull-out, fiber breakage and interlaminar delamination was distinguished from acoustic emission events amplitude range 30-45 dB (low amplitude events), 30-60 dB (low amplitude events), 60-80 dB (middle amplitude events), 80-97 (high amplitude events) and 60-85 dB (middle amplitude events), respectively.

In the present study, the mechanical behaviour of glass plain fabric/UP composites are investigated under off-axial tension loading conditions. Damage development and characteristics are investigated with acoustic emission (AE) techniques. Initial fracture point is obtained from three methods including knee point method, AE events method and AE energy method.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Materials and fabrication

The glass weave plain fabric, as illustrated in Figure 1, with areal weight of 570 g/m^2 , was used as the reinforcement and provided by Hokuriku Fiber glass Co., Ltd. Detailed information of glass plain fabric, such as linear density, yarn density and crimp rate, can be found in Table 1. Unsaturated polyester resin was (Showa: RIGORAC 150HRBQNTNW) used for matrix. The resin was mixed with the hardener MEKPO (PERMEK N; NOF Corporation) in a ratio of 100:0.7. These materials were used to fabricate hybrid composites with the hand lay-up molding method. First, gel coating was layered on the innermost layer, on which a sheet of glass weave plain fabric was layered with the resin. A sheet of gel coating was then layered on the outermost layer. It is important to ensure that bubbles are not trapped in between the fibers, thus, a steel roller was moved on the composite to remove trapped air. The thickness of the composites was controlled by spacers to get similar volume fraction of glass fiber. Finally, the blocks of the composite were pressed and naturally cured for 24 hours in ambient temperature, post cure was followed in an oven of $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ maintained 2 hours. After curing, the composite had a nominal thickness of 0.7 mm.

Figure 1: Photo of glass plain fabric.

Table 1: Detailed information of glass plain fabric.

Direction	Linear density (Tex)	Yarn density (N/25mm)	Crimp rate (%)
warp	1150	6.5	14.4
weft	1150	5.8	11.2

2.2 Tensile testing

Tensile tests were performed on the coupon specimens with the use of a 100-kN an Instron universal testing machine (55R4206) and extensometer of 50 mm gauge length according to the ASTM standard D3039. The crosshead speed with a loading rate of 1 mm/min was employed. Five kinds of plain coupon specimens with different fiber orientations ($\theta = 0, 5, 10, 15,$ and 30°) were cut from 300 mm by 300 mm composite panels. The off-axis angle θ is defined as the angle between the direction of loading and the warp direction of specimens. The tested composite specimens were rectangular in shape with dimensions $200 \times 20 \times 0.7$ mm, as illustrated in Figure 2. The cut edges were then smoothed using 200 Grade SiC paper. Rectangular-shaped tabs of 1.0 mm thick aluminum alloy were glued on both ends of the specimens with epoxy adhesive. The adhesive was cured at room temperature for 24 h. The tensile properties were reported after taking the average value of three measurements.

Figure 2: Geometry and dimensions of on-axis and off-axis specimen.

2.2 Acoustic emission

In order to discuss the fracture behavior, AE signals were monitored by 7600 series AE instrument (NF Corporation, Japan). The AE testing equipment and test parameters were as follows: AE data acquisition system; Physical Acoustic corporation Micro-30 sensors; 26dB preamplifiers having a bandwidth of 65-1100 KHz; system threshold of 30 dB; Peak definition time of 50s; hit definition time of 150 s; hit lockout time of 300 s. The sensor was attached to the specimen using elastic tape. Vacuum grease was used as a couplant between the sensor and the specimen surface. After setting, the AE signals were captured during mechanical testing by the software named "AEwin for USB". Signal descriptors such as amplitude, duration, rise time, counts, energy were calculated by the software.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Knee point method

The representative off-axis tensile stress-strain relationships of the glass plain fabric/UP composite specimens are reported in Figure 3 for all the fiber orientations. The on-axis stress-strain curve is smooth and nearly linear behavior is observed under on-axis (0°) loading. Under all off-axis tensile loading conditions ($\theta = 5, 10, 15,$ and 30°), a phenomenon of linear growth in preliminary segment and subsequently a significant nonlinear increase until ultimate catastrophic appeared. On the other hand, the off-axis tensile stress becomes lower compared to the on-axis tensile stress. The ultimate failure stress reduces dramatically with increasing off-axis angles in all cases. Furthermore, in almost all tests of the composites, even if no prominent variations are seen in the stress-strain curves, some sounds were heard before the final fracture, which is a clear evidence of some damage in the matrix prior to final failure. Knee point is a transition point, where the mechanical behavior begins to transform from linear behavior to nonlinear behavior (Figure 4). If the pre-set load exceeds the corresponding knee point, which shall cause unrecoverable fracture to the specimens. The corresponding initial fracture stress and stress can be obtained from this point.

Figure 3: Stress-strain curves of glass plain fabric/UP composites for various off-axis angles.

Figure 4: Definition of knee point diagram.

3.2 AE events method

The increased quickly point of AE events is considered possible to find the initial fracture, as shown in Figure 5. The applied stress and accumulative number of AE events as a function of the strain measured are illustrated in Figure 6 for various fiber orientations. In general, as shown in these figures, the AE activity initiates in the loading history indicating the occurrence of damage. The low AE events start at low strains, keep developing in the course of loading. Under off-axis tensile loading conditions ($\theta = 0, 5, \text{ and } 10^\circ$), the composites exhibit a non-linear behavior long before the first AE events are recorded. As seen in Figure 6, the initial fracture point obtained is 0.0008, 0.0011 and 0.001 (i.e. strain), respectively. For 15, and 30° loading conditions, on the other hand, the first AE events appear right after the stress-strain curve starts deviating from the Hooke's law. The corresponding initial fracture point is 0.0023 and 0.0026, respectively. Additionally, the accumulative number of AE events recorded for $\theta = 0, 5, \text{ and } 10^\circ$ is approximately 2.5 times greater than that for $\theta = 30^\circ$.

Figure 5: Definition of the initial fracture from an AE events diagram.

Figure 6: Deformation and AE response of glass plain fabric /UP composite specimens for various off-axis angle during tensile loading.

3.3 AE energy method

Based on the cumulative energy curve (Figure 7), two damage development thresholds can be identified: ϵ_{\min} (strain at which the first AE activity is recorded) and ϵ_t (transition strain, where the cumulative AE curve experiences a sudden jump into the domain of higher energies). These thresholds are also known as characteristic strains. Figure 7 illustrates how the strain thresholds ϵ_{\min} and ϵ_t are determined using AE diagrams with a logarithmic scale for the energy. The strain ϵ_t indicates the transition from one stage of damage development to another. This procedure is different from the one used to analyze damage development in the fiber direction [8]. Cumulative AE energy curves for all various fiber orientations are illustrated in Figure 8. It can be seen that there is a general trend for the curves at $\theta = 0, 5,$ and 10° to shift towards lower strain values. Thus, the first damage appears to start earlier at $\theta = 0, 5,$ and 10° . The following stages of damage development also seem to onset earlier at $\theta = 0, 5,$ and 10° . The diagrams of cumulative energy also reveal a striking difference among various fiber orientations: the cumulative energy of the acoustic events at different strain levels is significantly higher at $\theta = 0, 5,$ and 10° than the values at $\theta = 15$ and 30° . The sudden increase in the cumulative energy is clearly associated with the events of higher energy (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Definition of the damage development thresholds from an acoustic emission diagram in the logarithmic scale.

Figure 8: Cumulative AE energy as a function of the strain for various fiber orientations.

3.4 The comparison of initial fracture strain obtained from three methods

The comparison of initial fracture strain for various fiber orientations obtained from three methods including knee point method, AE events method and AE energy method is shown in Figure 9. It can be seen that initial fracture strain shows no obvious difference among three methods.

Figure. 9: The comparison of initial fracture strain obtained from three methods for various fiber orientations.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Off-axis tensile behaviour accompanied with acoustic emission (AE) registration of glass plain fabric /UP composite for various off-axis angles ($\theta = 0, 5, 10, 15$ and 30°) is examined. The results obtained can be summarized as follows:

1. The AE data revealed that the damage development thresholds are lower for the composites at $\theta = 0, 5,$ and 10° indicating an earlier onset of damage. The composites at $\theta = 0, 5,$ and 10° exhibited significantly increased AE activity, both in terms of the number of events and the energy level.
2. It is also found that initial fracture strain shows no obvious difference obtained from knee point method, AE events method and AE energy method.

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